

Psalms 109

also known as “Curses upon the Wicked”

Data source: Prayer in the Ancient World

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** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Northwest Semitic, Central Semitic, Hebrewic, Ancient Hebrew, Biblical Hebrew, Canaanite, Religious Group, Ancient Mediterranean, Prayer, Text, Near East, Language, Levantine Religion, Christianity, Curse, Semitic, Ancient Western Asia, Judah, Abrahamic, Israelite Religion, Yahwism, West Semitic, Israel, Afro-Asiatic, Judeans and Israelites, Judaism

Psalms 109 belongs to the fifth section of the Masoretic text's version of the book of Psalms (Pss 107-150), which begins the third part of the canon of the Hebrew Bible (known as the Writings, or *kētûbîm*). The book of Psalms (called *tēhillîm* or "Praises" in Hebrew) is an anthology comprising psalms of various origins, which were eventually edited into a codified collection. The earliest copies of Psalm 109 were found among the Dead Sea Scrolls. It appears in the Great Psalms Scroll (11Q5), which dates to 30-50 CE and reflects a different ordering of the psalms than the MT. It has been categorized as a psalm of individual complaint, the most common type of biblical psalm. Written in poetic language, Psalm 109 is one of 72 psalms in which David's name appears in the superscript, and, like the rest of Psalms, its authorship was traditionally attributed to him. Its actual origins and date of composition are unknown, though some have suggested it exhibits Persian influence, as well as a focus on the (restored) Temple, and thus dates to the late 6th century BCE (Gillingham 2022). Following a brief lament in vv. 2-5, Psalm 109 asks for Yahweh's retribution against those who have attacked the main speaker with false accusations and aggression for no discernible reason. The series of curses that follow in vv. 6-19 may be those of the supplicant or those of his antagonists. The prayer continues with another lament and a request for YHWH's intervention (vv. 20-29), and concludes with the promise that the supplicant will publicly praise YHWH for delivering him.

Date Range: 1000 BCE - 50 CE

Region: Ancient Israel/Judea

Region tags: Israel, Judean Desert

The setting within the psalm itself is Israel during the reign of King David (10th century BCE). However, it may have actually been composed in the late 6th century BCE. The oldest copies of the psalms were discovered in the Judean desert among the Dead Sea Scrolls.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Adele Berlin and Marc Zvi Brettler, eds., *The Jewish Study Bible*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Oxford

University Press, 2014).

– Source 2: John Goldingay, *Psalms, Volume 3: Psalms 90-150* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2008).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.stepbible.org/?q=version=OHB|reference=Ps.109&options=NUVHG>

– Source 1 Description: Online access to Hebrew and English versions

– Source 2 URL: <https://academic.oup.com/edited-volume/35006>

– Source 2 Description: *The Oxford Handbook of the Psalms*, edited by William P. Brown (2014)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Notes: The oldest copies of Psalm 109 come from the Dead Sea Scrolls (11Q5 and 4Q88) and date to the mid-first century CE.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: Parchment

Notes: The oldest copies of Psalm 109 come from the Dead Sea Scrolls (11Q5 and 4Q88) and date to the mid-first century CE.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The origin of the text is unknown, though it may have been composed in the late 6th century BCE.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

Notes: The oldest extant copies of Psalm 109 thus far discovered come from among the Dead Sea Scrolls found in the caves near Qumran in the Judean desert. How the text was stored/transmitted prior to that is unknown.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: The caves near Qumran do not contain images. However, previous copies of the text may have been stored in the Temple or elsewhere that may have contained images.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

Notes: It is likely that the text was read or performed aloud, though the context is unclear. It may or may not have been liturgical.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

Notes: The text is described in the superscription as belonging to David and is also associated with an unnamed religious or ceremonial leader.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

Notes: Though no longer considered alterable from the canonical form of the Masoretic text, the psalm appeared in collections with different orders in the Dead Sea Scrolls, which suggest that the ordering of this section of the book of Psalms was not yet fixed at that time.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Yes

Notes: There has long been disagreement in both early Jewish and early Christian circles about who the speaker(s) of vv. 6-19 might be (the psalmist or the ones who are harassing him).

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Yes

Notes: Scribes at Qumran are thought by scholars to have been male. Most literate individuals in ancient Israel and Judea were male.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: Though it can no longer be altered, at the time of the Dead Sea Scrolls the canon was still in flux. There were also additional psalms in copies from Qumran and in the Greek version of Psalms.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The language is Biblical Hebrew.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 1

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Who would have heard the psalm, if it was performed, is unclear. The stated audience is YHWH.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

– Large religious group (intolerant of other affiliations)

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– Yes

↳ How might emic and scholarly (anthropological) assessments of the audience differ?

– Specify: Though the prayer is ostensibly addressed to YHWH, no doubt it had a secondary audience of human listeners/readers.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: There were reformist movements during the Persian period and also at Qumran.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: Probably.

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Notes: It may have been sung.

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ On the reciter?

– Yes

Notes: The effect is presumably that YHWH will answer the supplicant's prayer.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Notes: It may have been sung.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Presumably the reader would receive YHWH's assistance with a similar situation.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: Unknown. It may have been sung or recited in liturgical contexts or in smaller contexts (family, small group) or by individuals ad hoc.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that its recitation/reading was accompanied by intoxicants.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: Copies of the Hebrew text are not accompanied by images. However, later, Christian copies of the Psalm 109 included imagery of Judas and/or the devil, as the psalm had become associated with Judas and Satan in some Christian traditions. For example, see the Stuttgart Psalter (fol. 126r) (Gillingham 2022: 179).

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There were multiple versions of the book of Psalms, with the psalms in different orders, at least until the first century BCE. There were also slight variations in the text through that time.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear how/why the version of the book of Psalms that is in the MT was selected.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: Though the canon was fixed in the first centuries CE, at the time of the Dead Sea Scrolls there was variation in the order and contents of Psalms.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Yes

↳ How are the volumes ordered?

– Specify: The Hebrew version of Psalms in the MT has 150 psalms, and is thought by scholars to contain five different groups of psalms.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?

(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The text contains ritual analogies (Wright 1994).

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: However, the text does reference David, and thus may obliquely refer to the David line of kings.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: It has been suggested that part of the text is presented as a type of legal case, brought before YHWH (Wright 1994).

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: However, the text specifies that the antagonist will be "cut off," their memory erased, and their children will suffer after their death.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text refers to the what will happen after the cursed person's death.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Field doesn't know

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Notes: The text suggests that the person who has antagonized the psalmist will not receive veneration after death.

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

Notes: However, elsewhere in book five of Psalms, YHWH is described as the God of Heaven. This may reflect Persian influence.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: However, David was viewed as chosen by YHWH.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

Notes: YHWH has covenant loyalty to the royal house and the Davidic line.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- Notes: YHWH is specifically asked to punish the psalmist's antagonist, sending his own curses back upon him.

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Notes: Not according to the canonical text of the Hebrew Bible. However, in practice, other supernatural beings may have been worshipped.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: YHWH is viewed as the leader of the court which will evaluate the case presented in the psalm.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: Note that this text does not describe YHWH communicating with humans specifically, other than through his actions on behalf of the supplicant. However, elsewhere in the Hebrew Bible YHWH communicates with humans, especially through prophets.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: YHWH's actions on behalf of the supplicant will be evident to the supplicant.

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– No

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Notes: The supplicant will recognize the actions of YHWH in the fulfillment of his request.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: YHWH is described in the text as both human-like and non-humanlike. For example, he can hear and respond to human words; however, it is not clear to what extent his physical form is envisioned as humanlike.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: YHWH will communicate through his actions on behalf of the supplicant. Elsewhere in the Hebrew Bible, YHWH can communicate with humans through words or visions or dreams, or via prophets.

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: YHWH will communicate through his actions on behalf of the supplicant.

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: There may be a hint of the divine council in the references to the court case being presented to YHWH through this psalm.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: YHWH's actions will be visible.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Notes: In this text, only thanksgiving and public praise is promised. However, elsewhere in the Hebrew Bible, animal sacrifice is practiced.

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– No

Notes: Not in this text. Elsewhere in the Hebrew Bible food regulations are present (e.g. Leviticus).

↳ Sacred space(s)

– No

Notes: Elsewhere in the Psalms, the Temple is a sacred space.

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - No
 - Notes: Not in this text.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - No
 - Notes: Not in this text.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - No
 - Notes: Not in this particular text, but elsewhere in the Hebrew Bible, yes.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
 - Notes: Not in this text, but elsewhere in the Hebrew Bible bravery is praised.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means
 - No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of bad luck?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Political failure?
 - No

- ↳ Defeat in battle?
 - Yes

- ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - No
 - Notes: Not in this particular text.

- ↳ Disaster on journeys?
 - Yes

- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - Yes

- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Yes

- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - Yes

- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - No

- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - Yes

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes

 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes

 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
- ↳ Highly emphasized?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of good luck?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of political success or power?
 - No
- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

Notes: Not in this particular text.

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

Notes: Not in this particular text, but elsewhere in the Hebrew Bible, yes.

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - Yes

- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– No
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A state

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: It is unclear to what degree the text was taught in ancient Israel/Judea. However, it seems clear that the text was studied and copied by the community who produced the Dead Sea Scrolls, and it was certainly studied in early Judaism.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: However, most literate individuals and scribes were men.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text may refer obliquely to the loss of sovereignty of Judah. It also uses war as a metaphor.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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